

1 Dxz4 locus silencing during germ layer specification in human embryonic stem cells.

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7 We describe Dxz4 locus silencing during germ layer specification in human embryonic stem cells. When
8 comparing the hES (embryonic stem cell) transcriptome to that of the differentiated germ layer
9 transcriptome, the quantity of FIRRE transcript was precisely maintained at equal quantity between hES
10 cell and the germ layer.

11 Xist stoichiometry observed in other cellular contexts, altered here, suggested that the activity of Xist and
12 associated loci and genes in this case - human stem cell lineage specification to the germ layers - was
13 characteristically altered because its function involved some use of the transcript that changed its quantity
14 in the steady state.

15 Differences in Xist and XIC-encoded transcript stoichiometry (ratio) were ascribed to a number of different
16 mechanisms that potentially included Xist ncRNA association with a epigenetic complex important for
17 development but resulting in loss or degradation of the ncRNA following regulatory function in the
18 specified program (germ layer transition), as well as other potential mechanisms that alter the cellular
19 ratio of Xist to FTX, TSIX and JPX, like separate Xist sequestration and subsequent silencing or other
20 function likely associated with the transcriptional regulatory function of the Xist RNP.